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Agronomic Zinc Biofortification in Oat

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Abstract

Biofortification is a noble technique to enhance the micronutrient absorption in cereal crops. Deficiency of zinc and other micronutrient are considered a severe diet and health challenges in human food. Moreover, zinc deficiency declines the growth and yield of oat. Therefore, the current experiment was conducted to evaluate the impact of various concentrations of zinc biofortification on agronomic and grain of oat. The experiment was performed in pots filled with 20 kg of soil by using CRD (completely randomized design) with factorial arrangements. The experiment was comprised of five Zn concentrations and two oat Cultivars (V_1 : S-2000, V_2 : S-2013) with three replications. Various crop parameters, i.e., time to start 50% germination, shoot and root dry weight, initial and final plant height, root and shoot length, number of leaves per plant, number of total and productive tillers, spike length, number of grain per spike and grain yield were observed and recorded information was statistically analyzed by Fisher's analysis of variance and averaged values of each treatment were compared with LSD (least significance difference) test having a 5% probability level. Results reported that application of zinc and cultivars significantly influenced the yield and yield contributing traits of oat. With respect to cultivars, maximum yield and yield contributing traits were recorded in S_2 (S-2013). With respect to the application of zinc T_2 and T_3 greatly influenced the yield and yield contributing traits of oat. Minimum yield and yield contributing traits were recorded in T_4 that concludes that higher application of zinc leads to toxicity in oat.

Keywords: Biofortification, Oat, Zinc, Nutrient deficiency

1. Introduction:

Micro-nutrients are an essential constituent of a living being. Zinc is micronutrient indispensable for bio-organism (Kaya and Higgs, 2002). It plays a vital role in plants, i.e., gene expression, amino acid production, protein biosynthesis, nutrient assimilation, pollen viability, fertilization, growth, and immunity (Alloway, 2004). In plants, zinc is an important part of proteins and enzymes, i.e., carbonic anhydrase, dehydrogenase and oxidase (Storey, 2007). Zinc is also very important for the human body as it plays an important role in controlling hunger pain and regulation of central nervous system (Branda *et al.*, 1995). Zinc is a cofactor of many enzymes (Grotz and Guerinot, 2006). Zinc involved in hormone production and bone growth in the human body (Ortega *et al.*, 1999). It regulates the estrogen level in the human body thus prevents obesity and heart diseases (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2010).

Deficiency of trace elements like zinc is a serious health problem all over the world (Gunes *et al.*, 2007). Over 100 million people are affected by zinc deficiency (Ma *et al.*, 2008). Approximately 40% of mothers and 54.2% childrens, mostly under the age of four years, are facing zinc deficiency in Pakistan (Bhutta *et al.*, 2007). Zinc deficiency causes diarrhea which is a common disease in the developing world (Maret, 2001; Ejaz and Latif, 2010). Zinc deficiency effects the growth and development of children as it causes diseases like diarrhea, skin lesions, weak immunity and reduces body weight (Samman, 2007).

Inadequate amount of zinc in soil reduces plant growth (Rehman *et al.*, 2012). Deficiency of zinc causes loss of membrane integrity make it more permeable and causes leakag, especially in roots as proved by potassium efflux rate (Ahmad, 2009). Insufficiency of Zinc reduces rice yield in Pakistan (Farooq *et al.*, 2009).

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Cultivation of high yielding cereal varieties is one of the major causes of zinc inadequacy in soil (Cakmak, 2008). People using cereals as staple food facing the problem of zinc deficiency. Cereals have a minimum level of zinc because cultivated in zinc-deficient soils (Cakmak, 2002).

Avena sativa is a cereal crop that belongs to the poaceae family, most widely used as grain food and for fodder purpose. Oat is a nutritious crop and mostly used as Oatmeal, Oat has the ability to reduce Cholesterol level in the body (Whitehead *et al.*, 2014). 100 g oat contains 16.9 g protein, 11.6 g fiber, 66.3 g carbohydrate, and 6.9 g fats. Furthermore, vitamin and minerals are present as 2 mg sodium, 4 mg zinc, 4.9 mg manganese, 5 mg iron, 54 mg calcium, 177 mg magnesium, 429 mg potassium and 523 mg phosphorous (Biesiekierski, 2017). Oat contains protein avenin, similar to the gliadin protein present in wheat; it can help in reducing celiac disease in human which causes failure to digest food properly (Vieille *et al.*, 2016).

Inadequate zinc supply in the soil causes a deficiency in cereals (Newell-McGloughlin, 2008). Present cultivars are deficient in zinc as compared to the wild type because wild type cultivar has a better ability to absorb nutrients particularly micronutrients (Cakmak *et al.*, 2004). When extra zinc is applied to the soil, zinc proportion in cereals like wheat and oat was increased as compared to the maize (Ortiz-Monasterio *et al.*, 2007). There are many techniques to increase zinc supply and assimilation in food like the supplementary application of nutrients, fortification of food during processing and changing nutrition value. However, all these techniques require inputs, resources, equipment, and trained labor, the current level of post-harvest fortification is inadequate to meet the requirements (Gomez-Galera *et al.*, 2010).

Increasing micronutrients in crop grains are termed as biofortification and is a good option to enhance the mineral content of the cereals (Rengel *et al.*, 1999). Zinc biofortification of cereals can be done by breeding and agronomic application of minerals (Waters and Sankaran, 2011). Agronomic mineral biofortification can be achieved by fertilizers application (Torun *et al.*, 2001). Application of minerals increases rice yield in paddy soils (Peck *et al.*, 2008). Agronomic biofortification methods include treatment of seeds with minerals, foliar application and seed priming with synthetic fertilizers (Harris *et al.*, 2008; Erenoglu *et al.*, 2011). There are many studies which show the efficiency of various methods of biofortification in cereals, but little work is done for oat. This study will add some new information regarding Zinc biofortification of oat in different cultivar at different concentrations, where zinc is applied as a soil amendment.

2. Materials and Methods:

This experiment was carried out to determine the effects of zinc biofortification on grain and grain quality of oat cultivars at University College of Agriculture, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan (31° 16.4' N; 71° 30.79' E; altitude of 128 m). Two high yielding and disease resistant oat cultivars, i.e., S-2000 and S-2013 and their response to five Zinc sulphate concentrations 0, 5, 10, 15, 20 kg hec^{-1} was tested in Pots.

The experimental soil was a sandy clay loam and belonged to the Lyallpur soil series. Soil samples were collected with soil auger up to the depth of 30 cm and passed through a sieve soil properties were soil series sultan pur, texture having silt loam comprise of sand 29.0%, silt 53.0%, clay 18.0%, organic matter 0.78%, available P content 1.8 mg kg^{-1} and available K content 9.0 mg kg^{-1} . Considering these properties recommended NPK was applied at the time of sowing and nitrogen in split doses.

The experiment was conducted by using completely block design (CBD) with factorial arrangements having three replications, net pot size 60 cm × 35 cm and each pot filled with 20kg soil. Pots were irrigated 15-17 days before sowing. Sowing was done manually; twenty seeds were sown in each pot, and after germination ten seedlings were maintained in each pot. Further irrigations were provided at a different stage, i.e., development of adventitious root, tillering, spike emergence, anthesis stage, milk stage and dough stage of grain formation. The first irrigation was applied to all treatments 25 days after sowing than according to the requirement and need of the crop. All other practices were the same.

Observations:

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During experiment different parameters were recorded, these parameters were, Days to start germination (50% observed few days after sowing, shoot length (cm), Root length (cm), Shoot dry weight (g), Root dry weight (g), Number of leaves, and number of tillers were calculated 15 days after sowing (DAS). Number of Productive tillers, spike length (cm), number of spikelets per spike and number of grains per spike were calculated at maturity.

Root and shoot length measurement (cm) (15 DAS)

After two weeks of germination, seedlings were heavily irrigated to soften the soil and to avoid root damage. Seedlings were carefully uprooted to measure root and shoot length of the individual seedling. Each seedling root and shoot length was measured by meter rod and mean value was computed (Harris *et al.*, 2008).

Root and Shoot dry weight measurement (g) (15 DAS)

After harvesting root and shoots were clipped with a knife, sundried for two days, oven dried at 70°C till constant weight and then dry weight was recorded to compute root and shoot dry weight per plant (Rehman *et al.*, 2012).

Spike length (cm), number of spikelets per spike and number of grains per plant

When crop reached harvest maturity, Spike length of oat was recorded with the help of the meter scale. Five random spikes were collected, and spike length was measured. Then the mean value was computed. Spikelet per spike and number of grains per spike were calculated from five selected spikes individually, and their average was calculated (Bhutta *et al.*, 2007).

Number of tillers and number of leaves

For a number of tillers and number of leaves per plant five plants were selected randomly and average values were calculated (Farooq *et al.*, 2009).

Number of productive tillers

Quadric was used to record a number of productive tillers from each treatment (Rehman, 2009).

Statistical Analysis:

After recording all observation from the experiment, recorded information was statistically analyzed by Fisher's analysis of variance and averaged values of each treatment were compared with LSD (least significance difference) test having 5% probability level (Steel *et al.*, 1997).

3. Results:

Results represent that zinc concentrations and oat cultivars significantly influenced by yield contributing parameters and grain yield of oat. Data regarding germination count was significantly influenced by oat cultivars, and various concentration of zinc and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations were also significant. With respect to oat cultivars maximum, i.e., 11.75 germination count was observed in V₂ (S-2013) and least, i.e., 9.37 was recorded in V₁ (S-2000). Similarly, with respect to zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 11.09 germination count was recorded in Z₃ (10 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 9.94 was documented in Z₅ (20 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹). Correspondingly with respect to plant height (after 15 days of sowing) was non-significantly influenced by oat cultivars. But the zinc concentration and interaction between zinc concentration and cultivars of oat was significant. With respect to zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 18.92 cm plant height (after 15 days) was documented in Z₄ (15 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 14.35 cm was recorded in Z₃ (10 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹). Similarly, plant height (after 21 days of sowing), was also non-significantly influenced by oat cultivars. However, the zinc concentration and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations were significant. With reverence to zinc concentrations maximum, i.e., 24.08 cm plant height (after 21 days) was documented in Z₄ (15 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 19.58 cm was recorded in Z₃ (10 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹). Shoot fresh weight (15 days of sowing) was significantly influenced by oat cultivars, zinc concentration, and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentration. With respect to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 20.53g

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fresh shoot weight was recorded in $S_1(S-2000)$, and least, i.e., 12.73g was observed in $S_2(S-2011)$. With respect to zinc concentration maximum, i.e. 21.17g shoot fresh weight was documented in Z_2 (05 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹), and least, i.e., 11.58g was observed in Z_3 (10 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹). Correspondingly, shoot dry weight (15 days of sowing) was significantly influenced by oat cultivars, zinc concentration, and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentration. With reverence to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 2.07g shoot dry weight was recorded in $S_1(S-2000)$ and least, i.e., 1.29g was observed in $S_2(S-2011)$. With respect to zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 2.14g shoot fresh weight was documented in Z_2 (05 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹), and least, i.e., 1.17g was observed in Z_3 (10 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹). Root fresh weight (15 days of sowing) was significantly influenced by oat cultivars and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentration, however non-significantly influenced by zinc concentration. With respect to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 12.33g fresh root weight was recorded in $S_1(S-2000)$, and least, i.e., 4.57g was observed in $S_2(S-2011)$. With respect to interaction between oat cultivar and zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 16.33g fresh root weight was documented in Z_3 (10 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and $S_1(S-2000)$, and least, i.e., 3.67g was observed in Z_1 (0 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and $S_2(S-2011)$. Similarly, data regarding root dry weight (15 days of sowing) was significantly influenced by oat cultivars and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentration, however non-significantly influenced by zinc concentration. With reverence to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 1.48g root dry weight (15 days of sowing) was recorded in $S_1(S-2000)$ and least, i.e., 0.55g was observed in $S_2(S-2011)$. With respect to interaction between oat cultivar and zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 1.96g root dry weight (15 days of sowing) was documented in Z_3 (10 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and $S_1(S-2000)$, and least, i.e., 0.44g was observed in Z_1 (0 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and $S_2(S-2011)$. Shoot length (15 days of sowing) was non-significant influenced by oat cultivars. However, the zinc concentration and interaction between oat cultivar and zinc concentration was significant. With reverence to zinc concentration maximum, i.e., 15.75 cm shoot length (15 days of sowing) was documented in Z_2 (05 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 10.92 cm was observed in Z_5 (20 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹). Root length (15 days of sowing) was significantly influenced by oat cultivars and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations. However, the zinc concentrations were non-significant. With respect to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 5.67 cm root length (15 days of sowing) was observed in $S_2(2011)$ and least, i.e., 4.57 cm was observed in S_1 (2000). With reverence to interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations maximum i.e. 6.50 cm root length (15 days of sowing) was observed in Z_4 (15 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and S_2 (2011) and least, i.e., 3.67 cm was documented in Z_1 (0 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and S_1 (2000). **No. of leaves (15 days of sowing)** was non-significantly influenced by oat cultivars and zinc concentrations and the interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations as shown in table # @@@@. Correspondingly, data regarding **no. of tillers (15 days of sowing)** was significantly influenced by oat cultivars and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations. However the non-significantly influenced by zinc concentrations. With respect to oat cultivar maximum, i.e., 7.00 no. of tillers were recorded in S_1 (2000) and least, i.e., 5.00 was observed in S_2 (2011). With the reverence of zinc concentrations and oat cultivars maximum, i.e., 8.00 was observed in Z_4 (15 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹, and S_1 (2000) and least, i.e., 4.67 cm was documented in Z_3 (10 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹), Z_5 (20 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and S_2 (2011). **Spike length** of oat was non-significantly influenced by oat cultivars and zinc concentrations, however the interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentration. Similarly, data regarding **no. of spikelets per spike** was significantly influenced by oat cultivars, zinc concentration, and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations. With respect to oat cultivars maximum, i.e., 30.40 no. of spikelets per spike was documented in S_2 (2011) and least, i.e., 23.73 was observed in S_1 (2000). In zinc concentrations maximum, i.e., 33.17 no. of spikelets per spike was observed in Z_2 (05 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 21.00 was recorded in Z_5 (20 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹). **No. of grains per spike** was significantly influenced by oat cultivars, zinc concentration, and interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations. With respect to oat cultivars maximum, i.e., 71.44 no. of grains per spike was documented in S_2 (2011) and least, i.e., 55.77 was observed in S_1 (2000). In zinc concentrations maximum, i.e., 77.94 no. of grains per spike was observed in Z_2 (05 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹) and least, i.e., 49.35 was recorded in Z_5 (20 kg $ZnSO_4$ ha⁻¹). Data regarding grain yield was significantly influenced by zinc concentrations and the interaction between oat cultivars and zinc concentrations. However, the grain yield was non-significantly influenced by oat

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cultivars. With respect to zinc concentrations maximum i.e. 68.55 g/pot was observed in Z₂ (05 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) that was statistically identical with Z₃(05 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) and Z₃ (15 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹) i.e. 65.38 g/pot and 64.20 g/pot respectively and least i.e. 52.69 g/pot grain yield was observed in Z₂ (20 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹).

Table1. Effect of different concentration of Zinc and Cultivars of oat on the germination count, plant height, shoot fresh weight, shoot dry weight, fresh root weight, root dry weight and shoot length of oat.

Treatments	S ₁	S ₂	Mean	S ₁	S ₂	Mean
	Germination count			Plant height (15 days)		
Z ₁	9.25 e	12.60 a	10.93B	19.33 abc	17.00 abcde	18.17 A
Z ₂	9.44 de	12.19 b	10.82B	16.33 bcde	16.33 bcde	16.33 AB
Z ₃	9.51 d	12.66 a	11.09A	13.67 e	15.03 de	14.35 B
Z ₄	9.38 de	10.64 c	10.01 C	18.00 abcd	19.83 ab	18.92 A
Z ₅	9.25 e	10.64 c	9.94C	15.83 cde	20.67 a	18.25 A
Mean	9.37B	11.75 A		16.63 ^{N.S}	17.773	
LSD value	0.2050			3.8086		
	Plant height (21 days)			Shoot Fresh weight (g) (After 15 days of sowing)		
Z ₁	23.17 ab	20.33 abc	21.75 AB	22.67 abc	13.67 cd	18.17 ABC
Z ₂	18.17 c	22.17 abc	20.17 B	27.33 a	15.00 bcd	21.17 A
Z ₃	20.67 abc	18.50 bc	19.58B	13.33 cd	9.833 d	11.58 C
Z ₄	24.17 a	24.00 a	24.08 A	23.33 ab	14.67 bcd	19.00AB
Z ₅	21.33 abc	23.83 a	22.58 AB	16.00 bcd	10.50 d	13.25 BC
Mean	21.50 ^{N.S}	21.77		20.53A	12.73 B	
LSD value	4.7749			9.4593		
	Shoot dry weight (g) (After 15 days of sowing)			Root Fresh weight (g) (After 15 days of sowing)		
Z ₁	2.29 abc	1.38 cd	1.83 ABC	7.67 bc	3.67 c	5.67 ^{N.S}
Z ₂	2.76 a	1.52 bcd	2.14 A	12.67 ab	5.33 c	9.00
Z ₃	1.34 cd	0.99 d	1.17 C	16.33 a	4.33 c	10.33
Z ₄	2.36 ab	1.48 bcd	1.92 AB	15.33 a	4.83 c	10.08
Z ₅	1.62 bcd	1.06 d	1.34 BC	9.67 abc	4.67 c	7.17
Mean	2.07 A	1.29 B		12.33 A	4.57 B	
LSD value	0.9554			7.1796		
	Root dry weight (g) (After 15 days of sowing)			Shoot length (cm) (After 15 days of sowing)		
Z ₁	0.92 bc	0.44 c	0.68 ^{N.S}	13.67 abcd	15.27 abc	14.47 AB
Z ₂	1.52 ab	0.64 c	1.08	15.00 abc	16.50 a	15.75 A
Z ₃	1.96 a	0.52 c	1.24	9.83 d	14.33 abcd	12.08 BC
Z ₄	1.84 a	0.58 c	1.21	14.67 abc	15.50 ab	15.08 AB
Z ₅	1.16 abc	0.56 c	0.86	10.50 cd	11.33 bcd	10.92 C
Mean	1.48 A	0.55 B		12.73 ^{N.S}	14.59	
LSD value	0.8616			4.7747		

S₁: S-2000; S₂: S-2011; Z₁: Control (0 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); Z₂:(05 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹);Z₃:(10 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹);Z₄:(15 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); Z₅:(20 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); ^{N.S} shows that results are non-significant. Any two means not sharing a letter differ significantly at 5% level of probability (LSD)

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Table2. Effect of different concentration of Zinc and Cultivars of oat on the root length, number of leaves, number of total tillers, no of productive tillers, spike length, number of spikelets per spike, number of grain per spike and grain yield of oat.

Treatments	S ₁	S ₂	Mean	S ₁	S ₂	Mean
	Root length (cm) (After 15 days of sowing)			Number of leaves (After 15 days of sowing)		
Z ₁	3.67 b	5.83 ab	4.75 ^{N.S}	5.67 ^{N.S}	5.67	5.67 ^{N.S}
Z ₂	5.33 ab	5.67 ab	5.50	6.33	5.33	5.83
Z ₃	4.33 ab	6.00 a	5.17	5.67	6.33	6.00
Z ₄	4.83 ab	6.50 a	5.67	6.00	6.33	6.17
Z ₅	4.67 ab	4.33 ab	4.50	6.33	6.33	6.33
Mean	4.57 B	5.67 A		6.00 ^{N.S}	6.00	
LSD value	4.7747			0.8950		
	Number of Total tillers (After 15 days of sowing)			Number of tillers (After 15 days of sowing)		
Z ₁	7.00 ab	5.00 ab	6.00 ^{N.S}	4.33 ^{N.S}	3.67	4.00 ^{N.S}
Z ₂	6.67 ab	5.00 ab	5.83	4.33	4.00	4.17
Z ₃	7.00 ab	4.67 b	5.83	5.33	3.67	4.50
Z ₄	8.00 a	5.67 ab	6.83	5.33	4.00	4.67
Z ₅	6.33 ab	4.67 b	5.50	4.67	3.67	4.17
Mean	7.00 A	5.00 B		4.80 ^{N.S}	3.80	
LSD value	2.4169			2.4169		
	Spike length of oat (cm)			Number of spikelets per spike at maturity		
Z ₁	18.33 b	20.00 ab	19.17 ^{N.S}	23.00 cd	26.00 bcd	24.50BC
Z ₂	20.00 ab	19.00 ab	19.50	26.00 bcd	40.33 a	33.17 A
Z ₃	20.67 a	19.33 ab	20.00	26.33 bcd	29.67 bc	28.00 AB
Z ₄	18.67 b	19.00 ab	18.83	25.00 bcd	32.33 ab	28.67 AB
Z ₅	19.00 ab	19.00 ab	19.00	18.33 d	23.67 bcd	21.00 C
Mean	19.33 ^{N.S}	19.27		23.73 B	30.40 A	
LSD value	1.8292			7.1796		
	Number of grain per spike			Grain yield		
Z ₁	54.05 cd	61.10 bcd	57.58BC	64.67 ab	60.33 abc	62.50 AB
Z ₂	61.10 bcd	94.78 a	77.94 A	71.33 a	65.77 ab	68.55 A
Z ₃	61.88 bcd	69.72 bc	65.80 AB	70.43 a	60.33 abc	65.38 A
Z ₄	58.75 bcd	75.98 ab	67.37 AB	55.33 bc	73.07 a	64.20 A
Z ₅	43.08 d	55.62 bcd	49.35 C	49.67 c	55.72 bc	52.69 B
Mean	55.77 B	71.44 A		62.29 ^{N.S}	63.043	
LSD value	21.490			14.414		

S₁: S-2000; S₂: S-2011; Z₁: Control (0 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); Z₂:(05 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹);Z₃:(10 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹);Z₄:(15 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); Z₅:(20 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹); ^{N.S} shows that results are non-significant. Any two means not sharing a letter differ significantly at 5% level of probability (LSD)

4. Discussion:

Results represent that zinc concentrations and oat cultivars significantly influenced by yield contributing parameters and grain yield of oat. The variation in environment and genetic characteristics results in altered germination count in oat cultivars. The cereal crops, i.e., maize, sorghum, rice, wheat, and oat cultivars germination count were significantly opposed by environmental variation and genetic characteristics of cereal cultivars (Zhao *et al.*, 2011; Nadim *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, germination count in oat cultivars was significantly influenced by zinc application but increase concentration of zinc in soil results to enhance the zinc toxicity and reduce germination count. Micronutrients are needed in the plant at low concentration and high application of zinc sulphate results to maximize toxicity and lowered the germination rate of cereals (Ahmed *et al.*, 2011; Habib, 2012). The genetic features in oat cultivars significantly influenced the plant height of oat. Zinc application plays a vital part in improving the enzymatic and photosynthetic activity of grain of oat. Low concentration of zinc significantly enhance various agronomic traits, i.e., leaves length, leaf area and shoot length that result to improve photosynthetic activity and shoot fresh weight of oat. The improvement in shoot weight results to enhance the dry shoot weight of cultivars of oat and zinc application significantly boost the dry shoot weight of oat (Erenoglu *et al.*, 2012). Optimum basal dose application of zinc significantly improves the

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root length of oat cultivars. The findings were identical with the results of Yassen *et al.*, (2010), who stated that the application of zinc result to improve the root, shoot fresh and dry weight of cereals. Results non-significant deviates the shoot length of oat cultivars due to environmental and genetic characteristics of oat. No. of leaves is genetic characteristics of oat cultivars that were non-significantly influenced by zinc application, that only influenced by the presence of heavy metals toxicity. The productive and total tillers of oat were significantly influenced by zinc application, but a high dose of zinc sulfate in soil results to minimize the total and productive tiller formation in cereals. Higher foliar application of zinc results to necrosis of cell tissues, damages the leaf structure, minimizes photosynthetic activity, disturb the source and sink assimilation and that minimized the grain yield of cereals (Narimani *et al.*, 2010). The findings were identical with the results of Khalifa *et al.*, (2011), who concludes that higher zinc application led to necrosis of tissues and minimized the yield production of oat. Spike length, no. of spikelets per spike and grains per spike area very important component in grain yield of oat, which was significantly influenced by the application of zinc (Arif *et al.*, 2006). The findings were identical with results of Asad *et al.*, (2003) and Sarkar *et al.*, (2007), who stated that zinc application significantly the agronomic traits and grain yield of oat.

5. Conclusion:

From the experiments, it was reported that the application of zinc and cultivars significantly influenced the yield and yield contributing traits of oat. With respect to cultivars, maximum yield and yield contributing traits were recorded in S₂ (S-2013). With respect to the application of zinc T₂ and T₃ greatly influenced the yield and yield contributing traits of oat. Minimum yield and yield contributing traits were recorded in T₄ that concludes that higher application of zinc leads to toxicity in oat.

6. References:

- i. Ahmad N, 2009. Establish soil and plant tissue boron and zinc requirement for cotton in calcareous soils of Pakistan. PhD. Thesis. University College of Agriculture Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Pakistan.
- ii. Ahmed W, Yaseen M, Arshad M & Ali Q. 2011. Response of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) to Foliar Feeding of Micronutrients. *Inter. J. Agro Vet. Med. Sci.* 5(2):209-220.
- iii. Alloway B.J. 2004. Boron deficiency in crops: An international perspective. p.34. In: Rashid, A. (ed.). *Boron deficiency in soils and crops of Pakistan: Diagnosis and Management*. Pakistan Agricultural Research Council, Islamabad, Pakistan.
- iv. Arif M, Chohan M.A, Ali S, Gul R & Khan S. 2006. Response of wheat to foliar application of nutrients. *J. Agric. Biol. Sci.* 1(4):34-36.
- v. Asad A, Blamey F.B.C & Edwards D.G. 2003. Effect of boron foliar application on vegetative and reproductive growth of sunflower. *An. Bot.* 92:565-570.
- vi. Bhowmik D, Chiranjib K.P & Kumar S.A. 2010. A potential medicinal importance of Zinc in human health and chronic disease. *Int. J. Pharm. Biomed. Sci.* 1:5-11.
- vii. Bhutta Z.A, Jiwani A, Feroze A, Kissana N & Monasterio I.O. 2007. Assessment of human zinc deficiency and determinants in Pakistan: Implications for interventions. In: *Proceeding of International Zinc Association conference 'Zinc Crops 2007-Improving Crop Production and Human Health'*. May 24-26, 2007. Istanbul, Turkey.
- viii. Biesiekierski J.R, 2017. "What is gluten?". *Can J. Gastroen. Hep.* 1: 78 81. doi:10.1111/jgh.13703. PMID 28244676.
- ix. Branda-o- Neto J, Stefan V, Mendoc B.B, Bloise W & Castro V.V. 1995. The essential role of zinc in growth. *Nutr. Res.* 15:35.
- x. Cakmak I. Torun A, Millet E, Feldman M, Fahima T, Korol A, Nevo E, Braun H.J & Ozkan H. 2004. *Triticum dicoccoides* L.: An Important genetic resource for increasing zinc and iron concentration in modern cultivated wheat. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 50:1047-1054.

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- xi. Cakmak I. 2002. *Plant nutrition research: Priorities to meet human needs for food in sustainable ways*. *Plant Soil*, 247:3-24.
- xii. Cakmak I. 2008. *Enrichment of cereal grains with zinc: agronomic or genetic biofortification?* *Plant Soil*, 302:1-17.
- xiii. Ejaz MS & Latif N. 2010. *Stunting and micronutrient deficiencies in malnourished children*. *J. Pak. Med. Assoc.* 60:543-7.
- xiv. Erenoglu E.B, Kutman U.B, Ceylan Y, Yildiz B & Cakmak I. 2011. *Improved nitrogen nutrition enhances root uptake, root-to-shoot translocation and remobilization of zinc (65Zn) in wheat*. *New Phytol.* 189:438-448.
- xv. Farooq M, Basra S.M.A, Wahid A, Khaliq A & Kobayashi N. 2009. *Rice seed invigoration*. In: E. Lichtfouse (ed.). *Sustainable Agriculture Reviews*, 137-175. Springer, the Netherlands.
- xvi. Gomez-Galera S, Rojas E, Sudhakar D, Zhu C.F, Pelacho A.M, Capell T & Christou P. 2010. *Critical evaluation of strategies for mineral fortification of staple food crops*. *Transgenic Res.* 19:165-180.
- xvii. Grotz N. & Guerinot M.L. 2006. *Molecular aspects of Cu, Fe and Zn homeostasis in plants*. *Biochem. Biophys. Acta.* 17(63):595-608
- xviii. Gunes A, Inal A, Adak M.S, Alpaslan M, Bagci E.G, Erol T & Pilbeam D.J. 2007. *Mineral nutrition of wheat, chickpea and lentil as affected by mixed cropping and soil moisture*. *Nutri. Cycl. in Agroeco.* 78:83-96.
- xix. Habib M. 2009. *Effect of foliar application of zinc and iron on wheat yield and quality*. *Afri. J. Biotech.* 8:6795-6798.
- xx. Harris D, Rashid A, Miraj G, Asif M & Yunas M. 2008. *A on-farm seed priming with zinc in chickpea and wheat in Pakistan*. *Plant Soil*, 306:3-10
- xxi. Kaya C & Higgs D. 2002. *Inter-relationships between zinc nutrition, growth parameters, and nutrient physiology grown in a hydroponically tomato cultivar*. *J. Plant Nutr.* 24: 1491- 1503.
- xxii. Khalifa R, Khan M, Shaaban S.H.A & Rawia A. 2011. *Effect of foliar application of zinc sulphate and boric acid on growth, yield and chemical constituents of iris plants*. *Ozean. J. Applied Sci.* 4:2.
- xxiii. Ma G.S, Jin Y, Li Y.P, Zhai F.Y, Kok F.J, Jacobsen E & Yang X.G. 2008. *Iron and zinc deficiencies in China: what is a feasible and cost-effective strategy?* *Public Health Nutr.* 11:632-638.
- xxiv. Maret W. 2001. *Zinc biochemistry, physiology, and homeostasis: recent insights and current trends*. 1st ed. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- xxv. Nadim M.A, Awan I.U, Baloch M.S, Khan E.A, Naveed K & Khan M.A. 2012. *Response of wheat (Triticum aestivum L.) to different micronutrients and their application methods*. *J. Anim. Plant Sci.* 22(1):113-119.
- xxvi. Narimani H, Rahimi M.M, Ahmadikhah A & Vaezi B. 2010. *Study on the effects of foliar spray of micronutrient on yield and yield components of durum wheat*. *Arch. Appl. Sci. Res.* 2(6):168-176.
- xxvii. Newell-McGloughlin M. 2008. *Nutritionally improved agricultural crops*. *Plant Physiol.* 147:939-953.
- xxviii. Ortega R.M, Quintas M.E & Andres P. 1999. *Zinc status of a group of pregnant Spanish women effects on anthropometric data and Apgar score of neonates*. *Nutr. Res.* 19:1423
- xxix. Ortiz-Monasterio I.J, Palecios-Rojas N, Meng E, Pixley K, Trethowan R & Pena R.J. 2007. *Enhancing the mineral and vitamin content of wheat and maize through plant breeding*. *J. Cereal Sci.* 46:293-307.
- xxx. Rehman H, Aziz T, Farooq M, Wakeel A & Rengel Z. 2012. *Zinc nutrition in rice production systems*. *Plant Soil J.* 60:543-7.
- xxxi. Rengel Z, Batten G.D, & Crowley D.E. 1999. *Agronomic approaches for improving the micronutrient density in edible portions of field crops*. *Field Crops Res.* 60:27-40.
- xxxii. Samman S. 2007. *Zinc. Nutrition & Dietetics*, 64(4):131-S134
- xxxiii. Sarkar D, Mandal B & M.C. Kundu. 2007. *Increasing use efficiency of boron fertilizers by rescheduling the time and method of application for crops in India*. *J. Plant Soil.* 301:77- 85

April 30, 2019

- xxxiv. Steel R.G.D, Torrie J.H & Dicky D.A. 1996. *Principles and procedures of Statistics, A biometrical approach*. 3rd Ed. McGraw hill, Inc. Book Co. N.Y. USA, pp. 352-358.
- xxxv. Storey B.J. 2007. Zinc. In: *Handbook of Plant Nutrition*. Barker, A.V., and D.J. Pilbeam, Ed., Taylor & Francis, USA. pp. 411-435.
- xxxvi. Torun A, Itekin I.G.A, Kalayci M, Yilmaz A, Eker S & Cakmak I. 2001. *Effects of zinc fertilization on grain yield and shoot concentrations of zinc, boron, and phosphorus of 25 wheat cultivars grown on a zinc-deficient and boron-toxic soil*. *J. Plant Nutr.* 24(11):1817- 1829.
- xxxvii. Vieille L.S, Pulido O.M, Abbott M, Koerner T.B & Godefroy S. 2016. *Celiac Disease and Gluten-Free Oats: A Canadian Position Based on a Literature Review*". *Can J. Gastroen. Hep.* 1870305. doi:10.1155/2016/1870305.
- xxxviii. Waters B.M, & Sankaran R.P. 2011. *Moving micronutrients from the soil to the seeds: genes and physiological processes from a bio-fortification perspective*. *Plant Sci.* 180:562-574.
- xxxix. Whitehead A, Beck E.J, Tosh S & Wolever T.M.S. 2014. *Cholesterol lowering effects of oat β -glucan a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trails*. *American. J. Agron.* 6; 1413- 1421
- xl. Yassen A, Abou-El-Nour E.A.A & Shedeed S. 2010. *Response of wheat to foliar Spray with urea and micronutrients*. *J. Am. Sci.* 6:14-22.
- xli. Zhao FJ, Lu X, Chen Z, Tian X & Yang X. 2011. *Zinc Fertilization Methods on Zinc Absorption and Translocation in Wheat*. *J. Agri. Sci.* 1:9752-9760.